

Studies on the Effect of Various Surfactants on Polarographic Maximum of Selenium (IV) in Presence of Mixed Electrolytes

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Selenium (IV) yields an acute sharp negative maximum in presence of $\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and calcium formate at -0.76 volts vs. S.C.E. The studies have been made in presence of anionic, non-ionic and cationic surfactants at $\mu = 0.30$ and 0.50 w. r. t. to the inert electrolytes. On connecting a high resistance of $10,000$ ohms in series with the cell the maximum is shifted to -0.80 V vs. S.C.E. Gelatin, camphor, lauryl pyridinium chloride (L. P. C.), cetyl pyridinium chloride (C.P. C.), methylene blue and Triton X-100 are the most suitable maximum suppressors. Electrocapillary curves in presence of these surfactants have been also studied. A probable mechanism of the suppression of the maxima has also been propounded in terms of the model pictures based on the triple layer theory.

After preliminary studies of Se (IV) by Schwaer and Suchy¹, a comprehensive approach was made in this direction polarographically by Lingane and Niedrach². The studies were carried out in presence of certain buffers of known pH as the supporting electrolytes. In highly acidic solutions the waves were split into several additional parts and at pH ranging from 4.85 to 5.90 a sharp maximum was reported. A single well-defined wave was obtained in presence of 1 M ammonium chloride, 0.003% gelatin and ammonia to bring pH in the range 8 to 9.5 maxima³ were reported in citrate buffers, phosphate buffers and borate-carbonate buffers.

In the present communication, an attempt has been made to study the effect of various surfactants in the suppression of maximum of Se (IV) which yields an acute sharp maximum in presence of barium chloride and calcium formate as indifferent electrolytes. The investigation has been mainly confined to study certain effects of a series of surfactants on the wave nature of Se (IV). The studies have been performed in presence of nonionic, anionic and cationic surfactants. The system under study constitutes of selenious acid (1 mM), mixed supporting electrolyte i.e. $\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ + calcium formate and the surface active substance (SAS). The various SAS used in this study are gelatin, triton X-100, camphor, methylene blue, pepsin, sodium salt of methyl red, cetyl pyridinium chloride (C.P.C.), lauryl pyridinium chloride (L.P.C.) and glucose. A preliminary study with the electrolytes AlCl_3 —calcium formate, AlCl_3 —sodium acetate, AlCl_3 —potassium oxalate, AlCl_3 —sodium potassium tartrate in presence of gelatin has also been made at $\mu = 0.50$.

EXPERIMENTAL

Electrolytes $\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, potassium oxalate, sodium acetate, calcium formate and selenious acid were of Analar B.D.H. grade. L.P.C. and C.P.C. were of commercial

1. L. Schwaer and K. Suchy, *Collection Czechoslov. Chem. Commun.*, 1935; 7, 25.

2. J. J. Lingane and L. W. Niedrach, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, p. 195.

3. Kolthoff and Lingane, "Polarography" Vol II, Interscience Publishers, New York, p. 565 (1965)

type, Triton X-100) was obtained from Rohm and Haas Co. Other surfactants were either of B.D.H. make or E. Merck.

Apparatus and technique: Pyrex glassware was used. The dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.) constituted of a standard capillary S-29417 (M/s E.H. Sargent & Co.). The capillary characteristics $m^{1/3} t^{1/6}$ was $2.35 \text{ mg}^{1/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/6}$ in the open circuit at constant height of mercury column. Temperature was maintained at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Lange's polarometer in conjunction with a Pye galvanometer was used for recording potential and current respectively. Deaeration was done by purified hydrogen generated in a Kipp's apparatus. Agar bridge saturated with ammonium nitrate was used for connecting the polarographic cell with the saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.). Pure mercury was used for d.m.e.

RESULTS

(A) *Studies with barium chloride and calcium formate at $\mu=0.30$.* A sharp acute maximum was obtained at $-0.76 \text{ V. vs. S.C.E.}$ in presence of barium chloride-calcium formate. All the studies were performed in presence of above said electrolytes with 0.001 M concentration of the depolarizer (Se) and the following surfactants.

(i) *Sodium salt of methyl red.*— 0.008% , 0.0016% and 0.0024% of sodium salt of methyl red was used in various solutions and in each case the maximum was obtained at $-0.76 \text{ V. vs. S.C.E.}$ The same solutions were studied polarographically by using resistances of 5000 ohms and $10,000 \text{ ohms}$ connected in series with the polarographic cell. With the increasing concentration of the surfactant, there seemed no measurable change in wave height as well in height of the maximum indicative of the fact that the diffusion coefficient of the depolarizer remained almost unaltered. With the appliance of 5000 ohms and $10,000 \text{ ohms}$ resistance in series, the maximum shifted to -0.78 V and -0.80 V , respectively. The result is in agreement with already reported by Brdicka⁴ and Lingane⁵ in case of other depolarizers. No shifts in electro-capillary maximum was registered revealing thereby that sodium salt of methyl red is more or less ineffective in elimination of maximum.

(ii) *Methylene blue.*—An aqueous solution of the dye was prepared and polarograms in presence of 0.004% , 0.008% , 0.012% and 0.016% dye were recorded. The height of the maximum was suppressed with the increasing concentration of the dye. The maximum was obtained at $-0.73 \text{ V. vs. S.C.E.}$ and on appliance of resistances of 5000 ohms and $10,000 \text{ ohms}$ in series with the cell it was shifted to -0.74 V and -0.756 V , respectively. In presence of 0.012% of the dye and $10,000 \text{ ohms}$ resistance the maximum was almost removed (Fig. I-B).

(iii) *Camphor.*— 0.002% , 0.008% alcoholic solutions of camphor were used. A dip was obtained in the potential range $0.5 \text{ V. to } -0.8 \text{ V.}$ preceded by a hump at -0.4 V. At -0.73 V , a sharp maximum appeared and it was shifted to -0.75 V. when $10,000 \text{ ohms}$ resistance was applied in series. At concentration 0.004% , the maximum got almost eliminated while at higher concentration (0.008%) the wave was totally obliterated owing

4. R. Brdicka, *Collection Czechoslov. Chem. Commun.*, 1936, **8**, 419.

5. J. J. Lingane, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 1665.

to the strong adsorptive influence of SAS. This has been further confirmed by the study of electrocapillary curves (Fig. II).

Fig. I. A. Effect of Sodium salt of methyl red (0.0024%) and resistance in series on the polarograms of Se (IV) 1 mM: 1. R=0, 2. R=5000 ohms & 3. R=10,000 ohms.
B. Polarograms of Se(IV) 1 mM in presence of methylene blue and resistance connected in series with the cell: 4. R=0, 5. R=5000 ohms & 6. R=10,000 ohms & 7. R=0, 8. R=10,000 ohms in presence of 0.004%, 0.016% methylene blue respectively.

Fig. II. Electrocapillary curves:
(a) 1. BaCl₂-Ca formate alone.
2. 0.002% Triton X-100.
3. 0.004% " "
(b) 1. 0.002% Camphor.
2. 0.004% " "
(c) 1. 0.008% Sodium salt of methyl red.
2. 0.016% " " " "

(iv) *Cetyl pyridinium chloride*. Polarograms in presence of 0.002%, 0.004%, 0.008% and 0.008% of C.P.C. were recorded. C.P.C. has got suppressive effect on the maximum. The effect of the resistance in series is the same as described earlier. L.P.C. has a tremendous effect on the wave nature of the depolarizer. The curve does not show any polarographic step as in presence of much L.P.C. the diffusion current is depressed enormously. The pH of the solutions remains almost constant=5.50.

(v) *Glucose*. An aqueous stock solution 0.4% of glucose was prepared. 0.004%, 0.008%, 0.016% of glucose solutions were used. The maximum was obtained as usual at -0.76 V. There is no appreciable change in the diffusion current indicative of the fact that viscosity is not increased with the increasing concentration of glucose. Thus glucose does not exert any suppressive effect on the stubborn maximum encountered at -0.76 V. vs. S.C.E.

(vi) *Triton X-100*. An aqueous stock solution 0.1% of triton X-100 was used and the resulting concentrations in the samples to be analysed were 0.001%, 0.002% and 0.004%. The maximum obtained is not so sharp as found in earlier cases and is rather a rounded one. 0.002% of triton X-100 removed the maximum. The interfacial tension is decreased with the increasing content of the surfactants which is evident from the electrocapillary curves (Fig. III).

(vii) *Gelatin*. Studies were conducted with a fresh aqueous solution of gelatin at the varying concentrations viz., 0.002%, 0.004%, 0.006% and 0.008%. The polarograms

are analogous to the cases reported earlier and maximum appeared at the same potential i.e. -0.76 V. When the resultant concentration of gelatin is 0.008% , the maximum is removed. (Fig. III).

(B) *Studies at ionic strength $\mu=0.50$.*

(a) In the preliminary studies $AlCl_3$ was used in the presence of calcium formate, sodium acetate, potassium oxalate and sodium potassium tartrate. In all these cases similar type of maximum is obtained at -0.76 V. vs. S.C.E. and the effect of gelatin as the maximum suppressor is studied. In case of $AlCl_3$ -calcium formate system, the maximum is sharp when ionic strength w.r.t. $AlCl_3$ is low and with the increasing μ w.r.t. $AlCl_3$, the wave does not show a polarographic step and the maximum is shifted to -0.72 V. vs. S.C.E. (Fig. IV).

(b) *Barium chloride and calcium formate system.* $M/4$ barium chloride and $M/4$ calcium formate were mixed together to give a mixed supporting electrolyte and the studies were made with the following surfactants at $\mu=0.50$.

(i) *Gelatin.* A sharp negative maximum is obtained at -0.77 V. vs S.C.E. with 0.002% gelatin. Further polarograms with gelatin concentration 0.008% , 0.01% , 0.015% , and 0.02% are recorded.

Fig. III. Polarograms of 1 mM Se (IV), in $BaCl_2$ -Calcium formate ($\mu=0.30$) in presence of: 1. 0.002% , 2. 0.004% , 3. 0.006% , 4. 0.008% gelatin and 5. 0.001% , 6. 0.002% and 7. 0.004% Triton X-100.

Fig. IV. Curves 1, 2, 3, 4 show the polarographic behaviour of Se(IV) in presence of calcium formate-aluminium chloride & 0.002% gelatin.

(ii) *Pepsin.* 0.002% , 0.004% , 0.008% and 0.016% pepsin was used in the solution for study. A sharp peak maximum appears at -0.77 V. vs S.C.E. and with the increase in pepsin concentration a slight depression occurs in its height. Pepsin seems to be of no avail in elimination of maximum (Fig. V).

(iii) *Congo red.* The dye assumes a violet colour in presence of selenious acid. The colour subsequently disappears in presence of barium chloride-calcium formate to give a yellow reddish solution. Higher concentration of the dye cannot be tried as precipitation occurs. Solutions with 0.002% , 0.004% , 0.006% and 0.008% of congo red were studied. Maximum is obtained at -0.78 V. vs S.C.E. in each case. The height is decreased with the increasing amount of congo red but it is difficult to eliminate the maximum altogether.

(iv) *Triton X-100 (non-ionic)*. Concentrations 0.001%, 0.002%, 0.004%, 0.008%, 0.012%, 0.016%, and 0.02% of triton X-100 were used. A sharp maximum obtained at -0.76V. is eliminated in presence of 0.002% SAS. Higher concentrations yield curve of the type (Fig. V).

(v) *Lauryl pyridinium chloride*. Polarograms with 0.001%, 0.002%, 0.004%, 0.005%, 0.012% and 0.016% of L.P.C. were studied. L.P.C. proves to be an efficient cationic surface active substance and suitable for the elimination of the maximum. At higher concentrations of the detergent, the wave does not exhibit any polarographic step (Fig VI).

DISCUSSION

The above studies have revealed the following characteristics concerning the nature of maximum in case of tetravalent selenium.

(a) The maximum is well pronounced sharp peaked one and appears in the range of -0.73 V. to 0.78 V., this potential varying slightly with the nature of SAS.

Fig. V. Polarograms of Se (IV) in presence of 1. 0.002%, 2. 0.004%, 3. 0.008% and 4. 0.016% Pepsin and in presence of Triton X-100 5. 0.001%, 6. 0.002%, 7. Higher concentrations.

Fig. VI. Polarograms of Se (IV) in presence of 1. 0.001%, 2. 0.002% and 3. 0.016% Lauryl Pyridinium chloride.

(b) The maximum is reproducible⁶ whether the e.m.f. may be varied in either direction the curve exactly retraces over the original curve. The maximum seems to be independent of the time of electrolysis.

(c) The sharp maximum with the increasing concentration of a suitable SAS, it develops into a rounded hump. This may be owing, in all probability to the strong adsorption of the surfactant. This is confirmed by study of electrocapillary curves which depict that in the presence of camphor, triton X-100 etc. the interfacial tension (or the drop time which being a measure of σ) decreases with increasing amount of the surfactant. A truncation⁷ of the electrocapillary curve results. This flattening is indicative of

6. Reference 3, Vol I, p. 156 (1963).

7. P. Zuman and I. M. Kolthoff, "Progress in Polarography", Vol I Interscience Publishers, p. 89 (1962).

strong adsorption (Fig. II). In the presence of excess of surfactant, the wave altogether disappears and this is caused owing to decrease in rate of electron transfer. As a part of the electrode (d.m.e.) surface may be blocked by a thin coverage of the adsorbed film and the rate of chemical step is decreased by the presence of adsorbed film⁸. At lower concentration of the depolarizer ($5 \times 10^{-4}M$) no maximum is obtained with the increase in the concentration of the electro-active material, an exaltation is noticed in the maximum but no generalisation can be made regarding the effect of concentration of the depolarizer on the height of the maximum.

(d) The maximum is of negative polarity. The negative maximum is susceptible to elimination in presence of cationic SAS e.g. L.P.C. as below

where D is the long chain residue. But exceptions to this generalisation are met with in literature⁹.

In the light of the above observations we find that congo red, methyl red, papain and glucose are unsuitable for the elimination of the maximum because these substances are only efficient in suppressing the maxima over a certain range of voltage and the adsorbability of these substances may reach a maximal value only at a fixed potential of mercury. The small decrease in instantaneous diffusion current in presence of these substances may be accounted for due to slight changes in viscosity.

A few mechanisms for the occurrence and elimination of maxima have been put forward by previous workers^{10,11}. However, a plausible mechanism for the removal of maximum is given below based on the considerations of the profile of the double layer (Fig. VII) put forward by Devanathan¹². The Helmholtz zone adjacent to the mercury

Fig. VII. Configuration of the electrical double layer. A. Devanathan's triple layer. B. In presence of non-ionic SAS. C. In presence of anionic SAS. D. In presence of cationic SAS.

8. L. Meites, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publishers, p. 325 (1965), 2nd ed.)
9. Reference 6, p. 164 (1965).
10. (a) J. Hryovský, *Actualites Scientifiques et industrielles*, Np. 90, Paris, 1934.
- (b) D. Ilkovic, *Collection Czechoslov. Chem. Commun.*, 1936, 8, 13.
11. H. J. Antweiler, *Z. Electrochem.* 1937, 43, 596.
12. M. A. V., Devanathan and P. Perics, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, 50, 373 and 1236.

drop (Fig. A, line a b) consists of unsolvated ions which may be specifically adsorbed there and further out from it exists layer of solvated cations and anions. Thus the Helmholtz layer is a duplex structure consisting of unsolvated ions and solvated ions. At the locus of the centres of the solvated ions (Fig. A, line c d) the diffuse Gouy and Chapman layer begins.

The configuration of the above mentioned double layer may be altered on the addition of the maxima suppressor in the following three ways :

(1) In case of nonionic surfactants viz., gelatin, triton X-100 etc. the capillary active SAS has got a strong tendency to penetrate deep into the Helmholtz zone (Fig. B) and gets adsorbed over the mercury surface. This retards the free passage of the ions of the depolarizer resulting in the elimination of maximum. In addition, it is also likely that some of the electro-active ions present already in the vicinity of the d.m.e. may be adsorbed on the molecules of SAS present there instead of getting stuck to the mercury drop.

(2) However, the long chains of the anionic surface-active agent bearing the polar head groups can not penetrate so deep as in the case of nonionic SAS. This is partly due to the orientation of the negative water seeking head groups and partly due to the repelling action of the negative mercury surface on these groups. Still, the penetration may be possible to some extent because of the electrostatic attraction between solvated ions and the negative polar heads (Fig. C). In such cases the ions of the depolarizer do get a passage through the pores of the SAS though in a controlled way and the normal conditions of concentration polarization may be achieved; this should eliminate the maximum. In fact, there are anionic SAS, which do eliminate the maximum. If, however, we consider the ζ potential increase owing to the presence of negative polar heads, the possibility of the removal of the negative maximum is obviated. The latter view is supported by the results obtained in the present work with anionic SAS which are found not to affect the maximum appreciably.

(3) If the surfactant has a positive polar head group, its orientation towards water (diffuse double layer) will be influenced on account of the repulsion between the solvated cations and positive polar charges. Consequently, penetration of the SAS in the Helmholtz plane may be minimum in this case (Fig. D) and double layer structure may not be as compact as in models B & C. This, however, does not completely prevent the SAS molecules from exerting their retarding influence on the passage of the depolarizer which finally leads to the depression of the maximum.

The important thing in this model picture is that because of the positive polar head groups the negative zeta potential will be diminished or positive zeta potential will be increased. This will increase the over-voltage and decrease the electro-reduction leading to the elimination of maximum.

Finally, it is also likely that interfacial viscosity which is enhanced due to adsorption of the SAS molecules may also hinder the passage of the electro-reducible ions and thus contribute partially towards the elimination of the maximum.

To sum up, the efficiency of the surfactants in the suppression of the negative maxima can be graded as follows :

Gelatin	>	L.P.C.	>	Pepsin
Triton X-100		C.P.C.		
Camphor		Methylene blue		(anionic)
(non-ionic)		(cationic)		

and this is in accordance with the above arguments.

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